

Fabrication of novel zeolite NaX@NaY/CuFe₂O₄ nanocomposite catalyst for decontamination of half mustard agent 2-chloro ethyl ethyl sulfide (2-CEES)

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Abstract

In this work, for the first time, CuFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully supported on the binary zeolite NaX@NaY by the ultrasonic-assisted hydrothermal method to gain the novel NaX@NaY/CuFe₂O₄ ternary nanocomposite catalyst. The as-fabricated nanocomposite was fully identified using FESEM, EDAX, XRD, FTIR, VSM, and BET analyses. Then, the performance of the NaX@NaY/CuFe₂O₄ nanocomposite catalyst for the decontamination of half mustard agent 2-chloro ethyl ethyl sulfide (2-CEES) was investigated by applying the GC-FID and GC-MS analyses. The achieved GC-FID results demonstrated that 2-CEES was completely decontaminated in the presence of NaX@NaY/CuFe₂O₄ nanocomposite in n-heptane solvent after 10 min of contact time. Lastly, ethyl vinyl sulfide (EVS) and 2-hydroxyl ethyl ethyl sulfide (2-HEES) as elimination and hydrolysis products of 2-CEES were identified, respectively. This displayed that the NaX@NaY/CuFe₂O₄ nanocomposite could potentially be used as a superior decontaminant of toxic chemical warfare agents.

Keywords: NaX@NaY/CuFe₂O₄, ultrasonic-assisted hydrothermal, decontamination, 2-CEES, EVS, 2-HEES.